

The transitions due to tribromide ion were observed at 25840 and 35971 cm^{-1} and those due to the HacacBr at 31446 and 45454 cm^{-1} .

Magnetic behaviour (Table 5) of iron(III) (high spin) is quite similar to that of manganese(II). The complex shows constant magnetic moment of 5.9 ± 0.1 B.M. in the temperature range 100-300 K. Which corresponds to five unpaired electrons of the high spin iron(III).

TABLE 5—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF $\text{Fe}(\text{HacacBr})\text{Br}(\text{Br}_3)_2$

Temp. K	$\chi M \times 10^6$ mol observed	$\chi M \times 10^6$ mol observed	μ_{eff} observed B.M.
100	42170	44936	5.80
150	28300	29957	5.80
165	27200	27234	5.99
176	24800	25532	5.90
188	24200	23902	6.08
200	22150	22468	5.95
240	18500	18723	5.94
260	17000	17283	5.94
280	16230	16048	6.02
300	14665	14979	5.98

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Formation Constant and Thermodynamic Functions of Some Trivalent Rare Earth Metal Complexes of *p*-Sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide

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LITERATURE survey reveals that no potentiometric studies have been done for the complex formation of trivalent rare earth metal ions with *p*-sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide (*p*-SUSASUD). In continuation to our earlier studies^{1,2} on Schiff base ligands and their metal complexes, we report in this paper the formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of trivalent rare earth metal ion complexes of Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} with *p*-sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide in aqueous medium at different temperatures and ionic strengths.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were either of AR grade or purified before use.

Preparation of the ligand: The ligand, *p*-sulpho-salicylidenesulphanilamide was prepared according to literature³. The purity of the compound was checked by its elemental analysis and melting point determination.

Solution: Double distilled water and carbonate free sodium hydroxide⁴ were prepared. Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The metal oxides were converted to metal perchlorates and then dissolved in 0.1 *M* perchloric acid solution. Estimation of the metal ions was done by EDTA method⁵.

Apparatus: A digital pH-meter of the Electronics Corporation of India, model 5651 (accuracy ± 0.01 units) with a combined glass electrode assembly was used. All the computations were carried out on an Electronics Corporation of India model EC 62 P programmable calculator.

Bjerrum-Calvin titration: The method of Bjerrum-Calvin^{6,7} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸ was followed to determine the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants. Following sets of titrations were performed at three different temperatures 32° ($\mu = 0.1$ *M* NaClO_4), 42° ($\mu = 0.1$ *M*, 0.05 *M* and 0.01 *M* NaClO_4), and 52° ($\mu = 0.1$ *M* NaClO_4).

Acid titration : 10 ml 0.1 *M* $\text{HClO}_4 + \text{NaClO}_4$ solution + water.

Ligand titration : 10 ml 0.1 *M* $\text{HClO}_4 + 4 \times 10^{-3}$ *M* ligand + NaClO_4 solution + water.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF *p*-SULPHONOSALICYLIDENESULPHANILAMIDE (*p*-SUSASUD) AND ITS COMPLEXES WITH RARE EARTH METAL IONS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS

Temp. °C	Ionic strength <i>M</i> NaClO ₄	H ⁺			σ*	Pr		Nd		Sm		Gd	
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log β _n ^H	log K ₁	σ						
32	0.1	10.14	6.76	2.30	0.03	7.04	0.16	7.70	0.18	8.43	0.17	8.27	0.14
	0.1	10.25	6.86	2.00	0.03	6.91	0.17	7.50	0.18	8.14	0.14	7.92	0.13
42	0.05	10.25	6.98	2.18	0.01	7.25	0.17	7.88	0.16	8.65	0.18	8.22	0.18
	0.01	10.27	7.15	2.23	0.01	7.76	0.16	8.33	0.17	9.23	0.16	8.75	0.15
	0.0	10.31	7.30	2.35	—	8.15	—	8.75	—	9.70	—	9.15	—
52	0.1	10.03	6.82	1.88	0.05	6.81	0.12	7.26	0.14	7.83	0.15	7.55	0.14

* σ = Standard deviation.

Metal titration: 5 ml 0.1 *M* HClO₄ + 5 ml 0.01 *M* metal solution + 4 × 10⁻³ *M* ligand + NaClO₄ solution + water.

The final volume in each set of titration was kept at 50 ml. Requisite amount of NaClO₄ solution was added in each set of titration to maintain the desired ionic strength.

Calculation: The proton-ligand formation constants (log K_n^H) were obtained from the proton-ligand formation curves, plotting the \bar{n}_H values⁹ against *pH* values. The values were also obtained by point-wise calculation method¹⁰ and agree closely. Only the mean values are given in Table 1.

From the ligand and metal-titration curves \bar{n} and *pL* values were calculated.

Results and Discussion

Owing to the very low concentration of metal ions used in the present investigation, the formation of polynuclear complexation was considered to be unimportant. The metal curves showed departure from the ligand curve at *pH* much lower than the *pH* of hydrolysis of the metal ions^{11,12} and this suggests that the liberation of proton is due to the chelation alone. The maximum values of \bar{n} was ~0.7, which indicates 1:1 complexation beyond the region of metal hydrolysis. From the formation curves obtained plotting \bar{n} vs *pL* the metal-ligand stability constant values (log K₁) were obtained as *pL* values, where $\bar{n} = 0.5$. The log stability constant values were also calculated by the following expression

$$\log K_1 = \log \frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} + pL \quad (1)$$

The log K₁ values along with the standard deviation (σ)⁹ are shown in Table 1.

The stoichiometric metal-ligand formation constants determined at 42° and at three different ionic strength 0.01, 0.05 and 0.1 *M* (NaClO₄) were extrapolated to $\sqrt{\mu} = 0$ to get the respective thermodynamic values (Table 1). It is evident from Table 1

that the formation constants decrease with increase in ionic strength of the medium. This is in agreement with the observation made earlier^{13,14}.

It was observed that with decreasing temperature the stability constants show an increasing trend. This suggests that low temperature is favourable for complexation. The thermodynamic parameters such as free energy change (Δ*G*), enthalpy change (Δ*H*) and entropy change (Δ*S*) were also calculated and the values are reported in Table 2. The log *K* values reported here are accurate to ±0.3 log units and the values of Δ*G*, Δ*H* and Δ*S* are reliable to ±0.04 kcal mol⁻¹, ±0.5 kcal mol⁻¹ and 2 cal mol⁻¹ deg⁻¹, respectively.

The enthalpy terms, Δ*H*, are favourable for complexation as reflected by their negative values in

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE METAL COMPLEXES WITH *p*-SUSASUD AT 42°

Cation	$\mu = 0.1 \text{ M NaClO}_4$			$\mu = 0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$
	-Δ <i>G</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	-Δ <i>H</i> kcal mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>S</i> cal mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	-Δ <i>G</i> ^o kcal mol ⁻¹
Pr ^{III}	9.96	4.68	+16.75	11.75
Nd ^{III}	10.81	11.24	-1.37	12.61
Sm ^{III}	11.73	14.52	-8.85	13.98
Gd ^{III}	11.42	17.33	-18.78	13.19

all the cases. The entropy terms, Δ*S*, for the complexes, other than Pr^{III}, are negative and hence not favourable for complex formation. However, the free energy change, Δ*G*, for all the complexes are negative suggesting thereby that the complex formation is a spontaneous one.

Rare earths with their 4*f* orbitals being well shielded usually form ionic compounds and are expected to obey the Born relationship¹⁵. The log K₁ values when plotted against *e*²/*r* show an increasing trend with a break at gadolinium. Certain amount of ionic character may, therefore, be suggested for the metal-ligand bonding although the possibility of some covalent interaction cannot be completely excluded¹⁶.

The stability constants of the trivalent rare earth metal ions follow the order : $\text{Pr}^{\text{III}} < \text{Nd}^{\text{III}} < \text{Sm}^{\text{III}} > \text{Gd}^{\text{III}}$.

Such difference in the trend of stability constants is not uncommon in the case of lanthanides¹⁷⁻¹⁹ and this may be traced to be due to the varying degree of stabilizations arising out of interactions of 4f metal orbitals with the ligand field²⁰.

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Kinetics of Discharge of Zinc(II) and Nickel(II) Ions at the D.M.E. in Dithiodipropionic Acid

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THE electrochemical behaviour of several mercapto compounds and their metal complexes has already been studied¹⁻⁶ in these laboratories and yielded useful results. This communication reports the polarographic reduction of zinc and nickel in presence of dithiodipropionic acid, the determination of kinetic parameters under various experimental conditions and the values of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for

the electrode reactions. The literature is, however, silent on these investigations.

Experimental

Dithiodipropionic acid (DTDPA) of 99% purity was supplied by Evan's Chemetics, New York. Zinc and nickel contents of zinc sulphate and nickel sulphate solutions were checked by estimating them as zinc pyrophosphate and nickel dimethylglyoximate. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Thymol was used as a maximum suppressor at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 1 M$) maintained by NaClO_4 .

C-V curves were drawn on a manual polarograph in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen using S.C.E. as the reference electrode with a thermostated H-cell. The capillary had the following characteristics: $m = 1.862 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$, $t = 3.66 \text{ sec}$, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.878 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$ at $h_{Hg} = 50 \text{ cms}$.

The current was recorded at the end of the drop-life instead of average current because the determination of kinetic parameters is based on Koutecky's method more accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current⁶.

Results and Discussion

The conventional log plots of the reduction waves of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in dithiodipropionic acid were straight lines but their slopes were not agreeing with the theoretical values indicating the irreversible nature of the waves in both the systems.

Effect of pH: Polarograms of 1 mM Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} in $0.04 M$ DTDPA and $1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$ were recorded in the pH range 1-7. It was observed that below pH 3.5 and above pH 5.5, the waves were not regular. However, a very well defined single cathodic wave was obtained at pH 4 where subsequent studies were carried out in both cases.

The values of half wave potentials in the case of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} at pH 4 were -1.006 and -0.84 , respectively. An examination of polarographic waves revealed that with increase in pH, the $-E_{1/2}$ displaced towards more negative potential showing the complex formation between $\text{Zn}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{2+}$ with DTDPA.

Effect of Hg pressure and temperature: The plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} (uncorrected) and temperature were found to be linear both in case of Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} .

The constancy of $i_d/h^{1/2}$ in each case and the values of temperature coefficients of i_d indicated the diffusion controlled nature of the waves.

Solutions of $0.04 M$ DTDPA and 1 mM Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} polarographed at temperatures 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50° showed that the $E_{1/2}$ shifted to more positive values with the increase in temperature